

Studies on Medium Effects. A Short Historical Survey

L. M. MUKHERJEE

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Fundamentals of the common methods for the estimation of medium effects for single ions, are briefly reviewed.

PHYSICOCHEMICAL behaviour of a solution is considered to be the manifestation of all conceivable interactions and/or changes involving the solute and solvent species in question. Thus, apart from the process of dissociation or aggregation of the solute molecules themselves, specific effects due to solvation of the various particles are expected to play a significant role in determining the overall property of a solution. Although the general importance of solvation and possibilities for correlating *emf* scales in different solvents in terms of the changes of activities and solvation energies of individual ions drew early attention of the chemists, real progress in this direction was long held up because the area was considered to be outside the purview of exact thermodynamics. This article presents a brief summary of the important extrathermodynamic approaches that have been suggested in course of time for the evaluation of single ion medium effects.

Single Ion Medium Effects. Definition :

The term ion medium effect has gradually come into use as a substitute for ion distribution coefficient which Bjerrum¹ first introduced long time ago. Other familiar alternative terminologies are : partition coefficient¹⁻³, degenerate activity coefficient⁴, medium activity coefficient⁵, solvent activity coefficient^{6,7}, coefficient of solvation and coefficient of transfer⁸, the last two being mostly confined to the French literature. In the molal scale, ion medium effect is normally denoted as $m\gamma_i$ (The suggested representation as $K_{S_2}^{S_1}$ ⁹ did not find favor) and the quantity $\log_m \gamma_i$ customarily expresses its numerical magnitude.

The activity of an ionic species *i* at a molality m_i , in a given non-aqueous solvent can be expressed in the manner

$$a'_i = m_i \gamma_i \quad \dots (1)$$

where γ_i denotes the salt-effect activity coefficient which becomes unity at zero molality in the same medium. When referred to the standard state in

water the activity a_i of the solute in the same non-aqueous solution can be related to its molality according to

$$a_i = m_i \gamma_i \quad \dots (2)$$

where γ_i is supposed to assume the value of one only at infinite dilution in water. As the value of m_i approaches zero, that of γ_i in the given medium approaches the value of the corresponding medium effect $m\gamma_i$. In other words, the activity coefficient γ_i of a solution, in a given non-aqueous solvent, referred to the aqueous standard state, is actually a product of the salt-effect activity coefficient and the medium effect $m\gamma_i$ of the ion.

$$\gamma_i = \gamma_i m\gamma_i \quad \dots (3)$$

Thus, from a consideration of the chemical potential, the difference between the standard free energies of an ionic solute in the non-aqueous solvent (sG_i°) and water (wG_i°) can be found equal to $RT \ln m\gamma_i$. Although this gives rise to a natural temptation of associating with medium effect a physical process of transfer of the solute species between water and the other solvent, it must be clearly borne in mind that in a "real" transfer process of a single ion of charge $\pm z$, one has to include an additional work term $\pm \psi z z$, where ψ denotes the potential at the interface of the two liquids. The free energy difference estimated from the medium effect of a single ion should, therefore, ideally represent the difference between its "chemical" energies of solvation and hydration. As is evident, this distinction between the "real" and "chemical" energies will, however, be non-existent in the case of a complete electrolyte or other electrically neutral combinations of ions.

Estimation of Single Ion Medium Effects. Postulates and Assumptions :

Application of the Born equation and its modifications-According to the original Born equation $\left[\Delta G^\circ = - \frac{Nz_i^2 e^2}{2r_i} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) \right]$, a major landmark in

the area, solvation of an ionic species depends on the charge and radius of the ion and the bulk dielectric constant of the medium. The difference in solvation energy of an ion between water and another solvent may be treated as the result of a sequence of processes, *viz.*, (i) discharging of the ion in water; (ii) transferring the discharged ion from water to the solvent in question; and (iii) restoration of the charge to the neutral species in that solvent. Although corrections based on the estimated contributions of other electrostatic terms related to ion dipole, ion-induced dipole, ion-quadrupole, dipole-dipole, and the dispersion forces (which are all functions of the ion radius in the order r^{-2} , r^{-4} , r^{-8} , r^{-3} , and r^{-6}) are indeed possible, a straightforward evaluation of the so-called "neutral component" of the solvation energy involved in step (ii) above still remains a principal handicap of the approach. (It may be added here that all suggested neutral analogs¹⁰ are subject to criticism on the ground that a neutral analog must have identically the same structure and size as the discharged ion; also, no structural dissimilarity between the solvent molecules held around the ion and those involved in any possible solvation of the neutral analog is to be permitted.)

Some workers contend that the simple Born equation is inadequate because of its use of crystallographic radius for the ions. So, additive correction to the ion radius has been proposed¹¹. In their attempts to relate the half-wave (or standard) potentials of the alkali metal ions in water and sulfolane, Coetzee *et al.*⁷ arrived at a cation-radius correction of 0.81 Å for the solvent sulfolane in an interesting manner. They used the radius correction of 0.72 Å for water and combined the solvation energy difference of Cs⁺ and Li⁺ ions, as obtained from the modified Born equation in water, with the difference between the differences in the half-wave potentials of the same pair of ions in water and sulfolane.

Potentiometric measurements :

a. *Assumption of negligible liquid-junction potential*—If the liquid junction potential E_j at the aqueous/non-aqueous interface of the cell

is eliminated or made negligible, medium effects for the proton, for instance, can be obtained using the relationship

$$E_{\text{cell}} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln m\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \dots (4)$$

Bjerrum and Larsson¹ proposed that the *emf* of the cell consisting of two Pt, H₂/H⁺ half-cells in water and methanol, which are connected by a 3.5M KCl salt-bridge, would be free from the liquid-junction potential and would thus provide a direct measure of the proton medium effect, methanol γ_{H^+} . For

obvious limitations, this approach was however abandoned until Parker and Alexander^{9b} revived the idea in the late sixties and suggested similar possibility for the determination of the medium effect of Ag⁺ (with methanol as the reference solvent) using a saturated tetraethylammonium picrate bridge to eliminate the junction potential between the two Ag/AgNO₃ half-cells used. Also, almost in the same vein, Parsons and Rubin¹² recently considered the possibility of constructing a cell *with an air-gap* between the half-cells for physically excluding the surface potential arising out of the liquid junction.

b. *Suggestion of the rubidium electrode*—While the above proposals for estimation of medium effects relate to the use of the standard potential data free from the liquid junction potentials, Pleskov¹³ introduced an alternative route, in 1947, by suggesting that the rubidium electrode be accepted as the standard. His suggestion apparently was based on the fact that rubidium ion with its large size, low charge and polarizability, and little tendency for solvation should involve small solvation energy in all solvents. As a result, the ion should have negligible medium effect. It is to be mentioned in this connection that Pleskov's rubidium proposal is credited as an important historic step in the development of the approaches primarily related to the use of large solutes.

c. *The ferrocene assumption*—In their investigation with a large number of metal-organic complexes having the metal in the adjacent oxidation states, Strehlow and his coworkers¹⁴ discovered that the ferrocene-ferricinium and cobaltocene-cobalticinium systems appear to fulfil the desired requirements for possible use as solvent-independent redox couples in comparing the *emf* scales between different solvents. In the ferrocene-ferricinium electrode, for instance, both members of the couple happen to be complexes of reasonably large size ($r=3.8$ Å for ferrocene) with the Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions "sandwiched" between two cyclopentadienyl ions. Besides, the reduced form is an uncharged molecule while the oxidized form carries only one unit of positive charge. Thus, one can foresee a good possibility in this case for the cancellation of the neutral component of the medium effect of the ferricinium ion with the medium effect of ferrocene. Moreover, due to the large size of the ferricinium ion, the residual electrostatic component of its medium effect can be expected to be small.

Application of the Hammett acidity functions—The theory of this approach is illustrated from a consideration of H₀ in the following case.

In a non-aqueous solution of an acid HA of molality m having the degree of dissociation α , one may express the Hammett acidity function H₀, using the indicator system B-BH⁺, according to the

relation.

$$H_0 = -\log m \gamma_{H^+} - \log m_{HA} - \log \alpha - \log s \gamma_{H^+} - \log \frac{s\gamma_{BH^+}}{s\gamma_B} - \log \frac{m\gamma_{BH^+}}{m\gamma_B} \quad (5)$$

where the $\log \gamma$ terms have their usual significance. Thus, if, in a given condition, the ratios of the salt-effects and the medium effects for the indicator system are held close to unity, the magnitude of $\log m\gamma_{H^+}$ can at least be roughly estimated.

Use of "reference electrolytes"—Applications of the "reference electrolytes" for medium effect determination essentially consist of solubility studies involving the three compounds tetraphenylphosphonium tetraphenylborate, tri-*iso* amyl-*n*-butylammonium tetraphenylborate, and tetraphenylarsonium tetraphenylborate, and combination of the results with those of any other insoluble salt having an ion in common. The first compound was introduced by Grunwald¹⁵, the second by Popovych¹⁶, and the third was used by Parker⁶. It is believed that due to the large size of the ions and the presence of an organic envelope around them, the electrostatic part of the solvation energy for such electrolytes will be small; also, for all the three systems, the possibility of specific interactions of the ions with a solvent should be low. Normally, the medium effects obtained for these electrolytes are equally apportioned between the corresponding cation and anion.

Extrapolation procedures involving the electrically neutral combinations of free energies—Assuming that the neutral component of the free energy of solvation is relatively unimportant for small ions, Izmaylov¹⁷ suggested some interesting extrapolation procedures to obtain ionic solvation energies, and hence medium effects. Since all electrostatic interactions would involve energies which are functions of different powers of the reciprocal of ion radius, r , it was considered possible to plot the average values of the electrically neutral combinations of free energies $G_M^\circ - G_H^\circ$ and $-(G_H^\circ + G_X^\circ)$ estimated from the

standard potentials, against $\frac{1}{\gamma_{ave}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_M} + \frac{1}{\gamma_X} \right)$ and

extrapolate the linear portion of the plot to $\frac{1}{\gamma_{ave}} = 0$, in order to determine the value of G_H° , that is, the free energy of solvation of a proton in a given solvent. Considering the solvation process to be essentially one of a donor-acceptor type of complex formation, Izmaylov¹⁸ later plotted the average values of similar electrically neutral combinations $(-G_i^\circ + \frac{G_M^\circ - G_X^\circ}{2})$ as functions of $\frac{1}{n^2}$, using iso-electronic pairs of systems (e.g., Na F, K Cl, Rb Br and Cs I), where n represented the principal quantum number of the lowest vacant orbital of M or X; the extrapolated value corresponding to $\frac{1}{n^2} = 0$ was presumed to give the value of G_i° in the particular medium.

Using a similar approach, Salomon¹⁹ lately derived single-ion free energies of solvation in water and propylene carbonate by extrapolation (to infinite ionic radius) of a plot of the differences of cation and anion conventional energies²⁰ for ions of equal radii vs. $\frac{1}{\gamma_i}$.

General Observations :

Although and discussion of the results derived from the individual extrathermodynamic assumptions has not been intended for this review, it is to be briefly remarked that, in certain instances, substantial disagreement among the values of medium effect obtained from different approaches has been noticed. It should, however, be stated that these discrepancies are not typical of the particular assumptions used. For pertinent details, the readers are referred to some of the earlier reviews^{9,21,22} and the original literature²³⁻²⁴ on the subject.

In addition, it should be mentioned at this point that a wealth of information on the gas-phase chemistry has accumulated in the meantime, which offers valuable insight into ionic solvation in general and permits determination of some of the fundamental thermodynamic quantities²⁵⁻⁴⁴. Furthermore, the water-gas phase distribution coefficients, which are useful in ascertaining the intrinsic hydrophilic character of compounds, should be valued as important supplements in the general context of medium effect studies. The apparent connection of these distribution coefficients with natural processes such as loss of flavor components from the largely aqueous foodstuffs and transfer of pesticides and other compounds between various bodies and the atmosphere, is remarkable and may indeed be of particular interest to some workers⁴⁵.

Finally, one should keep it in view that in spite of the correlations that have been possible through the extrathermodynamic assumptions or models presented above, there still exists considerable demand for fresh approaches in this direction along with sophisticated theoretical studies and independent verification of the results.

References

1. N. BJERRUM and E. LARSSON, *Z. physik. Chem.*, 1927, 127, 358.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF and S. BRUCKENSTEIN, "Acid-Base Equilibria in Non-aqueous Solutions" in *Treatise on Analytical Chemistry*, I. M. Kolthoff and P. J. Elving, eds., Interscience, New York, 1959, Vol. 1, Part 1, Chap. 13.
3. H. A. LAITINEN, *Chemical Analysis*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1960, Chap. 4.
4. E. GRUNWALD and B. J. BERKOWITZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4939; E. GUTBEZAHL and E. GRUNWALD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 559, 565.
5. J. F. COETZEE and J. J. CAMPION, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 2517.

6. (a) R. ALEXANDER and A. J. PARKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 5549.
6. (b) A. J. PARKER and R. ALEXANDER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 3313.
7. J. F. COETZEE, J. M. SIMON and R. J. BERTOZZI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 766.
8. J. COURT-COUCPEZ and M. L. DEMEZET, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1967, 4744; C. BARRAQUE, J. VEDEL and B. TREMILLON, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1968, 3421.
9. I. M. KOLTHOFF, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1971, **25**, 305.
10. M. ALFENAAR and C. L. DELIGNY, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1967, **86**, 929; G. R. HAUGEN and H. L. FRIEDMAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4549.
11. W. M. LATIMER, K. S. PITZER and C. M. SLANSKY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 108; E. J. W. VERWEY, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1942, **61**, 127.
12. R. PARSONS and B. T. RUBIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1976, **70**, 1636.
13. V. A. PLESKOV, *Usp. Khim.*, 1947, **16**, 254.
14. H. M. KOEPP, H. WENDT and H. STREHLOW, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1960, **64**, 483.
15. E. GRUNWALD, G. BAUGHMAN and G. KOHNSTAM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5801.
16. O. POPOVYCH and A. J. DILL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 456.
17. N. A. IZMAYLOV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1959, **126**, 1033; *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1960, **34**, 2414.
18. N. A. IZMAYLOV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1963, **149**, 884, 1103.
19. M. SALOMON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 2519.
20. H. F. HALLIWEL and N. C. NYBERG, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 1126.
21. O. POPOVYCH, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1970, **1**, 73.
22. L. M. MUKHERJEE, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **4**, 325.
23. N. A. IZMAYLOV, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, 1963, **149**, 1364.
24. I. M. KOLTHOFF and F. G. THOMAS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 3049.
25. B. CASE, N. S. HUSH, R. PARSONS and M. E. PEOVER, *J. Electroanal Chem.*, 1965, **10**, 360.
26. G. CHOUX and R. L. BENOIT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6221.
27. J. COURTOT-COUCPEZ, C. MADEC and M. L. DEMEZET, *C. R. Acad. Sci., Paris, Ser. C*, 1970, **270**, 1397.
28. J. F. COETZEE and R. BERTOZZI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, **43**, 961; *Anal. Chem.* 1973, **45**, 1064.
29. I. M. KOLTHOFF and M. K. CHANTOONI, Jr., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 2024; *J. Phys. Chem.* 1973, **77**, 523, 527.
30. L. M. MUKHERJEE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 243.
31. R. ALEXANDER, A. J. PARKER, J. H. SHARP and W. E. WAGHORNE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 1148.
32. O. POPOVYCH, A. GIBEFISKY and D. H. BERNE, *Anal. Chem.* 1972, **44**, 811.
33. R. L. BENOIT and P. PICHET, *J. Electroanal Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1973, **43**, 59.
34. M. L'HER and J. COURT-COUCPEZ, *J. Electroanal. Chem. Interfacial Electrochem.*, 1973, **48**, 265.
35. P. KEBARLE, S.K. SEARLES, A. ZOLLA, I. SCARBOROUGH and M. ARSHADI, *Adv. Mass Spectrom.*, 1968, **40**, 621.
36. S.K. SEARLES and P. KEBARLE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 2619.
37. A. GOOD, D. A. DURDEN and P. KEBARLE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1970, **52**, 222.
38. I. DZIDIE and P. KEBARLE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 1466.
39. I. DZIDIE, A. GOOD and P. KEBARLE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 664.
40. M. ARSHADI and P. KEBARLE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 1483.
41. I. D. PAYZANT, R. YAMDAGNI and P. KEBARLE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1971, **49**, 3308.
42. R. YAMDAGNI and P. KEBARLE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 7139; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 3504, 4050.
43. J. B. CUMMING and P. KEBARLE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 1.
44. G. H. PARSONS, C. H. ROCHESTER and C. E. C. WOOD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (B), 1971, 533; G. H. PARSONS, C. H. ROCHESTER, A. ROSTRON and P. C. SYKES, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin II*, 1972, 136.
45. J. HINE and P. K. MOOKERJEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 292.